

THE ROLE OF STAKEHOLDERS IN SUPPORTING THE HOSPITAL TOWARDS MEDICAL TOURISM SERVICES

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Abstract

This paper describes the potential of medical tourism and looks at how a policy (regulation) is needed in the development of this program. Medical tourism is seen from a systems approach by involving stakeholders consisting of the government, community, media, academics, and entrepreneurs. All stakeholders have their respective roles in supporting the course of medical tourism in Siak Regency. This research uses descriptive-qualitative analysis model, the authors took primary data in the form of interviews and took data from at least 213 people in Siak Regency to represent the entire community, as well as secondary data collection methods. The scope of this paper is medical tourism in Siak Regency. The results of this study indicate that each stakeholder has its own challenges in preparing for medical tourism. Policies in facilities and infrastructure must be improved according to international standards. From the human resources sector, there must be a change in the form of training and certification of skills that support public services on an international scale. The potential for medical tourism is very large to keep Indonesians from going abroad and increase the number of foreign tourists who come. However,

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INTRODUCTION

Siak Regency has the potential to generate income from the tourism sector. From year to year, local and foreign tourist visits in Siak Regency continue to increase where in the last 5 years, starting in 2017 as many as 328,628 tourists, in 2018 as many as 386,938 tourists, in 2019 as many as 618,019 tourists, then in 2020 as many as 112,128 tourists (the decline occurred due to the covid-19 pandemic), and in 2021 as many as 164,388 tourists. (Central Bureau of Statistics for Siak Regency BPS-Statistics of Siak Regency, 2021) To increase the number of tourists, a tourism innovation will be developed, namely medical tourism. The reason medical tourism is a consideration is that Indonesia loses around 97 trillion rupiah of potential income because around two million people prefer to go on medical tourism to Malaysia, Singapore, Thailand and the United States. (Princess, 2022)

Medical tourism is currently a growing industry with a focus on providing services for local patients and foreign patients (other countries) in hospitals. Hospitals must focus on improving quality, building infrastructure, networks, and minimizing costs to attract foreign patients due to intense competition. In medical tourism, apart from hospitals and patients, other stakeholders also play an important role such as the government, medical travel facilitators, vendors (who actually supply medicines, equipment, other materials to hospitals), and the community (around patients). (Chakraborty and Poddar, 2020) All stakeholders contribute to the process of

developing a sustainable tourism (in this case medical tourism). Stakeholder engagement leads to the framing of concepts. According to the concept of Erick T. Byrd(2007), the success rate of a tourism innovation lies in the stakeholders involved. Other researchers in this area are Angelo Presenza, Maria Cipollina(2010)who said that the intensive relationship of tourism companies with policy makers was critical to the sustainability of the tourism. Public sector stakeholders also play a bigger role in both management and marketing activities compared to the private sector because they have a much higher position.The role of stakeholders is to support by using an effective strategy in developing medical tourism by designing a stakeholder network of medical tourism entrepreneurs and the provincial council of medical tourism clarifying the roles and responsibilities of stakeholders.(Jabbari et al., 2013)The key to the success of medical tourism is also supported by highly skilled professionals, advanced medical equipment, and well-established infrastructure are factors that contribute to the rapid growth of medical tourism in South Korea.(Hwang, Lee and Kang, 2018)

There are many supporting factors why medical tourism was chosen as a new type of tourism that will continue to develop. Various studies provide several reasons. The benefit of profit is one of the main reasons (Beladi,Chao, et al, 2019; Hanefeld, Horsfall, et al,2013; Cabinova, Gallo, et al,2021). The ability to gain access to more advanced care and better costs are also strong reasons (E. Borg, 2018). Geographic proximity, specialized medical facilities, reputation, and cultural proximity, are also very important factors for medical tourists(Virani, Wellstead and Howlett, 2020). Geographical proximity and cultural similarities drive the large number of patients. However, it must be balanced with improved services such as the ease of smooth immigration procedures, better and more attractive tourist attractions and an enhanced personal touch to customers.(Yusof, Rosnan and Shamsuddin, 2020). Improvement of superior technology, expertise in the medical field, and quality of service(Borg, 2018; A. Kamassi, et al, 2021;Hwang, Lee and Kang, 2018)This is the reason why many medical tourism in developing countries are successful. The factor of currency differences also significantly affects medical tourism(Dhale, 2020). According to Alireza Jabbari et al(2013),the medical tourism industry requires strategic planning and coordination among key actors (stakeholders).It is imperative to establish a provincial medical tourism board, assign key responsibilities, and delegate the necessary powers to stakeholders.To realize this commitment to date, there has been no visible commitment from the stakeholders where the role and responsibility of the stakeholders is still low. There are different stakeholders in the medical tourism industry. Thus, policy makers can plan, make policies and decisions, and use effective strategies to develop medical tourism by designing a network of medical tourism stakeholders, medical tourism provincial councils, and clarifying the roles and responsibilities of stakeholders.(Jabbari et al., 2013)

The author sees a gap in achieving medical tourism. The author sees the gap that occurs right in the middle between stakeholders and medical tourism, namely the policy (policy) where there are no things that regulate medical tourism. A support is needed in the form of national and regional policies (regulations) in regulating the course of medical tourism to be implemented. Research on the role of stakeholders in making policies in medical tourism services is still lacking, so research is needed to fill the gap. The selection of Siak Regency

became the locus because there was no research on the relationship between medical tourism and stakeholders discussed in previous studies.

This study aims to determine and analyze the role of stakeholders in supporting hospitals towards medical tourism services at Tengku Rafi'an Hospital, Siak Regency. This research is expected to provide information related to the role of stakeholders in supporting hospitals towards medical tourism services. For further, it is hoped that this research can be a reference for future researchers to discuss similar themes

LIBRARY REVIEW

Medical Tourism Stakeholders

Jamal and Getz(1995)identify stakeholders related to the tourism industry as local governments, public institutions, Chambers of Commerce and Industry, local tourism authorities, and resident and social organizations (NGOs). Medical tourism stakeholders include the central government setting medical tourism policy, medical tourism businesses, and related organizations. A. Kamassi, et al(2021)see the term stakeholder is used to describe the main stakeholders involved in the medical tourism industry. The level of involvement among these stakeholders may differ, but they are considered a key component in the medical tourist decision-making process. They are the initial data provider for medical tourists to choose their medical tourism destination.The author uses the term stakeholder or key stakeholders which consists of five aspects which include the government, academia, society, entrepreneurs, to the media related to medical tourism. These stakeholders have an important role in the realization of medical tourism, especially in Tengku Rafi'an Hospital, Siak Regency.

Medical Tourism

Medical tourism can be defined as the process of traveling abroad for the purpose of receiving medical treatment(Tomislav Meštrović, 2018). The growing popularity of medical tourism has attracted the attention of policy makers, researchers and the media. Originally, the term referred to the journey of patients from less developed countries to developed countries in pursuit of treatments that were not available in their homeland.(Tomislav Meštrović, 2018) Medical tourism emerged as a result of consumers being faced with a wider choice of medical services and the exponential growth in the global healthcare market. Combining the terms "medical" and "tourism", the main target is patients who visit other regions or countries for treatment. Therefore, the medical tourism industry is directed at significant efforts to fulfill the people's desire for better health with quality medical care. The net worth of the worldwide medical tourism market was estimated at \$61,172 billion in 2016 and is expected to increase to \$165.3 billion by 2023.(Hwang, Lee and Kang, 2018)

In the context of this research, the author describes medical tourism not only focusing on medical services and visits to get medical treatment, but also as a tour to get to know Siak Regency which will be explored with holiday packages in medical tourism. So that visitors can not only enjoy medical services, visitors can also take a vacation and enjoy the beauty of Siak Regency.Henceforth in this paper, medical tourism will refer to the phenomenon of patients

seeking affordable and available medical treatments or procedures abroad while at the same time paying attention to the consumption of tourism services.

Medical Traveler

Medical tourists are tourists who are dissatisfied with the health care system in their respective countries and have the option of traveling abroad that is more affordable and has more complete services.(Aziz et al., 2015)Advances in technology make it easier for medical tourists to find information related to medical services that are both in terms of quality and price. This also encourages medical service providers to focus on providing services to foreign patients.(Enderwick and Nagar, 2011) these foreign patients can come from areas that share a common culture or deliberately travel long distances to get what is not available in their country.

Healthcare Provider

Kamassi, Abd Manaf and Omar (2020) see that health service providers are the spearhead in medical tourism. Without health care providers, medical tourism is impossible. A recent trend in global healthcare is the privatization of healthcare providers whose systems are based on the wishes of the patient. Health care providers maximize the potential to attract local and foreign patients. Service providers usually have something special that is not found elsewhere, such as anti-aging clinics. Health care providers offer professionals who use sophisticated and modern equipment, low costs, to non-medical aspects such as modern, comfortable, and luxurious facilities.(Hwang, Lee and Kang, 2018)In this paper, the health service provider is the Tengku Rafi'an Regional General Hospital (RSUD) Siak Regency.

Medical Tourism Policy

The role of the government as the main stakeholder is very important in determining medical tourism policy. Forms of government support for medical tourism are regulation and promotion through mechanisms and strategies adapted to national development planning, tourism campaigns, establishment and appointment of government agencies, to support that facilitates the running of medical tourism programs for service providers to prospective medical tourists.(Kamassi, Abd Manaf and Omar, 2020)Indonesia's medical tourism policy has been made to serve as a reference in the implementation of Indonesian medical tourism. The policy is stated in Permenkes 76 of 2015. The plan for developing medical tourism has been rolling since several years ago. The idea of medical tourism departs from the potential per capita expenditure of the Indonesian people for health needs every year. The Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy together with the Ministry of Health have established four medical tourism concepts. First, medical tourism, secondly wellness and herbal tourism, thirdly sport health tourism, and fourthly health scientific tourism.(Rosana, 2021).

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN VARIABLES

System Approach

The author uses a systems approach and the concept of medical tourism to analyze more deeply the relationship between stakeholders in supporting the realization of medical tourism at Tengku Rafi'an Hospital, Siak Regency. Medical tourism itself cannot be separated from tourism phenomena that exist in systems theory such as political, economic, socio-cultural, and environmental factors. The form of core stakeholder support in this case is Permenkes 76 of 2015

Picture 1: System Approach

The author then examines the writings of Wiweka and Arcana(2019)to see a systems approach in tourism. This paper divides tourism into a system which is divided into internal sub-systems and external sub-systems. In the internal sub-system, there is a demand for tourism. This demand can be seen from two sides, namely the economy such as people who have the ability to travel, including the determinants of their trip, and psychology which is seen from the motivation and behavior of tourists who travel. Then, the internal sub-system also has an intermediary who is the liaison between tourist demand and tourism supply. Its characteristics and efficiency play an important role as a bridge, either to attract tourists or even used by tourists to reach their destination. Tourism supply is also part of the internal sub-system. The tourism supply element offers everything to attract tourists. It offers a mix of tourism products and services consumed by tourists. The external sub-system consists of international trade factors, security and security factors, natural or climatic factors, socio-cultural factors, technology, economic or financial factors, political factors, demographics, and geographical factors. All of these factors have an influence on tourism technology, economic or financial factors, political factors, demographics, and geographical factors. All of these factors have an influence on tourism technology, economic or financial factors, political factors, demographics, and geographical factors. All of these factors have an influence on tourism

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The author uses descriptive qualitative research to explain the phenomena in this study. The research location is Tengku Rafi'an Hospital, Siak Regency, and Riau Province. This location determination is based on medical tourism which will be carried out after the support of stakeholders. This study uses primary data by determining several sources who will become part of stakeholders such as government, media, community, businessmen, and academics. Secondary data is also used in the form of previous studies from journals, books, to websites that have researched similar issues. The author will process the existing data and analyze the data which will be developed in this paper. This paper uses a Systematic Mapping Study (SMS) in looking at the existing approaches to discussing the perspective of this paper. This research involves interviews with stakeholders and involves a survey to the community. After collecting research data, the next process is to analyze the data to be developed so as to produce accurate and valid data

The author begins the data collection process by compiling a list of stakeholders (government, media, community, academics, and entrepreneurs). Furthermore, the authors contacted key informants such as the Regent of Siak Regency and the Chairman of the Siak Regency DPRD who represented the government. Furthermore, the author also contacted resource persons who each represented the media, academics, and entrepreneurs. For community representatives, the authors took data as much as 213 people as representatives of the entire Siak community. Data were collected as part of an overall research project on medical tourism in Siak District. In particular, interviewees were asked about medical tourism and their support for tourism innovation and medical services and how they capture new tourism opportunities in Siak District.

Interview data collection was carried out in face-to-face meetings, via telephone, focus group discussions and meeting meetings. Especially for community data collection, the author distributed a google form to get their views on medical tourism and see the form of support and output they want to get. Interviews were conducted with one key stakeholder informant. To qualify as a key informant, the interviewee must be an agency, experienced, and hands-on practitioner.

RESEARCH RESULT

Four Stakeholders

The author presents evidence of stakeholder synergy in the system that builds medical tourism as a new tourism development in Siak. Each stakeholder has a different role and view in medical tourism. The government supports all forms of medical tourism development. Tourism is indeed a facility that Siak wants to develop after previously holding national and international level tourism. The role of the government in this regard is to facilitate the process of developing medical tourism aimed at attracting even greater numbers of tourists. Furthermore, the government which in this case is in charge of the supervisor, namely the

DPRD of Siak Regency also supports by providing supervision to the prospects and development of medical tourism in Siak. When referring to the systems approach,

Furthermore, there are constructive inputs from academics. In supporting medical tourism, at least the main organizer, in this case is the Tengku Rafi'an Regional General Hospital, must be the main supporter so that visitors feel safe. Starting from the Emergency Installation (IGD) which must be better prepared, equipped, and must be stronger in responding to any emergency conditions that will be faced. In addition, if you want a strong and rooted medical tourism, medical specialty is needed according to the potential of the area. The potential that exists must be explored in depth and packaged with an attractive appearance for tourists. To realize all these things, the strategy needed is a high commitment of regional leaders, preparation and synchronization across sectors.

The media are also part of the stakeholders in this paper. The media is ready to encourage socialization to the public about the importance of medical tourism to the needs of the community. The most important goal and challenge of medical tourism is to ensure that local people (Indonesia) do not go out of the country for treatment first. Press personnel have a role in sharing information about how medical tourism reaches the public. This is reflected in the middle and upper class people who no longer seek treatment in Siak, but instead go to Pekanbaru, Jakarta, and even go abroad. In addition, the role of the media in this case is as a reminder to the government to focus and be serious in managing medical tourism. Service quality equal to international quality must be a concern where if international tourists come, they deserve international standard service. If not, then it is only considered as a normal tour. Improvement of human resources related to services must be increased on an international level.

Next are the entrepreneurs who are also part of the stakeholders. From an entrepreneur's point of view, medical tourism will be a huge potential in increasing local business. Culinary and lodging entrepreneurs are businesses that must be seriously reviewed. For this reason, if regulations (policies) have been issued, then entrepreneurs are ready to provide what they can provide to the fullest. They have a role in giving a special taste to medical tourism guests who not only seek treatment, but also travel around Siak Regency. Typical food must be packaged more attractively accompanied by better prepared human resources. Employers ask for government support such as training in preparing international standard human resources.

COMMUNITY OF SIAK DISTRICT

The author takes community data as many as 213 people as representatives of the people of Siak Regency as a whole. The goal is to gain in-depth insight regarding the form of public views and knowledge about medical tourism. Of the 213 people who were taken, 62.4% were women and 37.6% were men. The majority age is 31-40 years with a total of 108 people. The majority of education is Strata 1 (S1) with a total of 142 people.

Picture 2: Medical Tourism Knowledge

Picture 3: Medical Visits Abroad

Picture 4: Agree or Disagree With Medical Tourism

Picture5: Potential Overseas

Based on the data taken, 33.3% of the public did not know/unfamiliar with the previous term medical tourism. However, when the question was replaced with the term medical visit to Malacca or abroad, the number of people who were not familiar with this term decreased to 11.7%. Of the 213 people whose data was taken, 21.6% had made a medical visit to Malacca or abroad. Based on this data, the majority of people support medical tourism in Siak Regency. However, as many as 3.8% did not agree with medical tourism for reasons that the service was not yet excellent at this time. If medical tourism is already running, the potential for residents who make medical trips abroad decreases to 8%.

DISCUSSION

This study aims to see and investigate how medical tourism is influenced by the responses and needs of stakeholders. This is the main point of this research regarding medical tourism in Siak Regency. To be fully implemented, medical tourism requires a policy from stakeholders. Of course, the roles of stakeholders, which in this paper are the government, society, academics, media, and entrepreneurs have their respective roles in determining the course of medical tourism considering this will attract foreign tourists. which of course requires a tourism system (in this case medical) to provide services that are of international standard. The author finds that there is a role for each stakeholder in the development of medical tourism. Based on this analysis, the authors suggest the following:

Proposition 1: Medical tourism creates market opportunities

Medical tourism is influenced by market demand. In another sense, the economic strength of the medical tourism provider country affects the course of this program. However, medical tourism also becomes a big market opportunity (economy developing) if it becomes a national strategy. The development trend of medical tourism involves not only the trade in medical services but also involves a combination of many sectors: travel, hospitality, safety, health systems, government strategy, destination management and marketing, education, research, sustainability, etc.(Ile and igu, 2017)The direct economic impact will be felt by many people, especially businessmen who will interact economically with foreign tourists who come. However, from the data we got, there is a challenge in welcoming foreign guests. The problem is the author presents as follows;

Proposition 2: Human resources must be prepared according to international standards

Increasing human resources in supporting medical tourism is urgently needed by stakeholders. This is because medical tourism encourages individuals or groups to cross international boundaries to access medical care in areas that are targeted by medical tourism. This process requires the readiness of competent human resources. If it does not adapt, this will encourage a global distribution of workforce, both health and other sectors that provide direct services to tourists. There are at least some potential migrations that occur in medical tourism such as long-term international migration, long-term diaspora migration, long-term (generally) migration, and some short-term migration.(Snyder et al., 2015)To address this, policymakers

should work to ensure changes in the training and licensing of health workers and public services to promote the medical tourism sector. Based on this, shows that;

Proposition 3: Each stakeholder has a different problem and solution

Each stakeholder has a different role and problem in medical tourism. Of course, every problem has a different approach and solution. The author finds that there are at least some problems regarding medical tourism in Siak. Facilities and infrastructure are something that continues to be a concern from the point of view of the government, as well as the community. Then, the service shows results that have been accepted by the general public, but there are several percent of the community who state that the service must be improved again. The issue of knowledge of medical tourism must be improved in order to support the success of medical tourism in the future. Although each stakeholder has different concerns, they are united in strategies that are ready to be focused and included from the government level to the community.(Jabbari et al., 2013).

Proposition 4: Medical tourism can reduce the rate of medical visits abroad

According to the data that has been taken, there are layers of society who have never heard of the term medical tourism before. However, once they hear the term medical visit to Malacca or abroad, the level of understanding increases dramatically. Previously, people believed in services and health workers in other countries and offered more affordable prices. When people hear that medical tourism will be held in Siak Regency, they welcome it enthusiastically and it is predicted that it will reduce the number of local tourists abroad, especially the people of Siak Regency and can become a role model for national medical tourism. Located not far from competing medical tourism (Malacca), Siak can be a data sample in suppressing the number of Indonesian tourists visiting abroad. Besides that,

Proposition 5: A regulation that regulates medical tourism is needed

Rules (regulations) are things that the government must pay special attention to. There are several considerations to be taken such as; the government must regulate medical tourism by improving everything needed by thinking there are disagreements with other stakeholders in managing and implementing medical tourism, the large medical tourism sector should be a major consideration (interest) to be realized immediately, and national and international level accreditation is needed to add domestic regulations. This includes, a global governance consideration that protects competitive and foreign resources that will occur as a major concern in Guatemala(Labonté et al., 2018).

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

Medical tourism is a new tourism breakthrough where patients not only visit to get medical assistance, but also travel there. Literature studies have not discussed much about how a medical tourism should be supported by regulation (policy). There are at least five stakeholders involved in medical tourism in Siak, namely the government, community, academics, media,

and entrepreneurs. Each stakeholder has different problems and solutions, but they are all connected in a system to support medical tourism. Facilities and infrastructure are the main things that must be repaired and improved according to international standards. There are at least five propositions that can be input in the future, namely; 1) Medical tourism creates market opportunities; 2) Human resources must be prepared according to international standards; 3) Each stakeholder has a different problem and solution; 4) Medical tourism can reduce the rate of medical visits abroad; 5) A regulation that regulates medical tourism is needed.

SUGGESTION

There needs to be a policy initiative (regulation) that regulates and manages medical tourism in Siak to run well. Empowerment of human resources is also an important thing to do because it can threaten the competitiveness of foreign workers who are free to work (ASEAN members).

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